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Women in Rabindranath Tagore's Selected Short Stories from Sabuj Patra

Abstract

The short stories of Rabindranath published in *Sabuj Patra* marks an important phase in his understanding of the social position of women as well as his views on exploitation of women, women rights, women independence and deprivation of women. In an interview published in the *Forward Magazine*, the author had divided his short stories into two categories naming them as 'Earlier stories' and 'Later stories'. The short stories like 'Streer Patra', 'Haimanti', 'Bostomi' and 'Dena Pawna' delved deep within the two- sided aspect of women, positioning on one hand the family orientation and on the other hand as a free spirited seeker of truth. In doing so, we can see the victimised figure of the woman rise in her silence as in the case of Anila. It is however not only in silence that Tagore's characterisation of women is exemplified the women characters rise above traditional values despite their loneliness and reach out for self-evaluation. From a literary perspective these stories have much psychological value as they reflect women's self-announcement in a major way.

Keywords: *Sabuj Patra*, *Forward Magazine*, *Earlier Stories*, *Later Stories*, *Women Rights*, *Women Independence*, *Self-Announcement*, *Two- Sided Aspect of Women*, *Streer patra*, *Haimanti*, *Dena Pawna*, *Bostomi*, *Psychological Value*, *Social Position of Women*, *Exploitation*, *Loneliness*, *Seeker of Truth*, *Family Orientation*, *Victimised*, *Silence*, *Self-Evaluation*, *Values*, *Deprivation*.

Introduction

Rabindranath himself had the realisation that much of his stories as published in *Sabuj Patra*, were much more independent in their nature. In his older days Rabindranath felt a special affection for the stories from the *Silaidaha Padma yapan parva*. Rabindranath had himself often critically compared the stories of the first and second series of short stories published in *Sabuj Patra*. In his interview¹ published in the *Forward magazine* Tagore had said:

"They (the early stories) have the freshness of youth...my later stories haven't got that freshness..."²

His view regarding the next series of stories as expressed in that same interview is as follows:

"they have greater psychological value and they deal with problems...my stories of a later period have got the necessary technique...but I wish I could go back once more to my former life."³

This interview was published on 23rd February 1936, and this clearly indicates that Rabindranath was mentioning about the later stories published in *Sabuj Patra*. The psychological value of the stories published in the *Sadhana* magazine in the Bengali year of 1301 was of no less significance, for example stories like 'Megh o Roudra' or 'Nishithe'. Despite this we show a special affection for his stories published in *Sabuj Patra* because it was written during a transitional phase in Rabindranath's literary oeuvre. This phase of writing not only revealed his understanding of human psychology but also remarkably exposed a novel viewpoint. These stories also reveal a unique understanding of male female relationship and mutual behaviour. In his old age Rabindranath reshaped his old story in to a much modern context and created the story of *Tin Sangee*, which was often criticised by many and some even revolted against this experimentation.

Review of Literature

The concept of 'women' in Tagore is a much discussed issue. However, such discourses have not been considered from multiple vantage points. For a long time much of the literary criticism centered on character and story analysis. However since we are focussing on the issue of women in Tagore's *Sabuj Patra* short stories, it can be said that it is of immense

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